

Efficacy and Work Outcomes: Mediating Role of Employee Engagement

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ABSTRACT: Organizations are facing many challenges because of competitiveness, innovation, and employee's disengagement. The purpose of the study was to give empirical direction to the conceptual framework of the study and to investigate the mediating role of employee engagement (EE) between efficacy and organizational work outcomes. Convenience sampling was used to collect the data through questionnaire from respondents. The empirical evidence of the study depicted that Efficacy and its three components self, collective and organizational efficacy have direct impact on work outcomes (WO) and on its three components that are innovation, effectiveness and competitiveness whereas the impact of EE on WO is significant and partial mediation exists between Efficacy and WO relationship. The finding of the study gives implications to HR managers in investigating the perception of employees toward work outcomes. Second, the academic significance of the study is that it explores the knowledge of work outcomes. Finally, this study provides insights about the mediating role of EE on efficacy and organizational work outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Self-efficacy, Collective-efficacy, Organizational-efficacy, Employee engagement, Work outcomes, Innovation, Effectiveness, Competitiveness